

A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON THE DYNAMICS OF MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE ORGANISATION

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ABSTRACT

Management is a tool for the successful growth and development of an organisation. As opined by Peter F. Drucker father of Modern Management., Management is life blood, and oxygen to the corporate level business organisation. Continuous flow of healthy blood, breathing fresh natural oxygen is very important for the survival of human beings. In the same way, the healthy and best practices, timely decisions, strong determination, unity of direction, unity of command and well- functioning, efficient human services monitoring, action planning, healthy working culture, and inspiring motivational activities of management etc., are very much required for the successful growth and development of organisation. The efforts and activities of management are continuous in nature. And the existence of management is a mandatory in the organisation since long time.

Management and administration lead the organisation towards the accomplishment of objectives and predetermined goals. Management is a goal setter, trouble shooter. and target achiever. In every modern corporate level business organisation like public sector Company organisations, Joint stock Companies, and in even in multinational corporations, management plays an important and significant role.

In this chapter, certain dynamic concepts of fundamentals of H. R. management thoughts, strategies of workforce management, recruitment & selections, maximum utilisation of H. R. Services administrative dimensions of management, functions, power of decision-making, centralisation and decentralisation, delegation of powers, management by objectives and the role of different streams of management, theories of management, X and Y theories nature and speciality of scientific management- contributions of F.W. Taylor, Principles of management drafted by Henry Fayal are the topics which were discussed., for the conceptual understanding of U.G and P.G. level students of Commerce and management course, as they are the targeted group of this chapter.

Keywords: (Mandatory., Determination, Dynamics, Centralisation and Decentralisation, Targeted group, Multinational corporations., delegation of powers, scientific management, management by objectives).

INTRODUCTION:

Management is the extracting the works done by the people, workers, and employees for the accomplishment of objectives and predetermined targets through the various functions and activities. For processing the activities in the organisation, management will initiate it

through decision making. According to a Prof. MOORE decision making function may be called as management. Management mainly deals with resources and objectives and goals. Management is efficient in usage of resources of human capital, material, and Technology for achieving the target of productivity and maintaining the quality in the products and services. Management discharges, the various functions like planning, direction, control, coordination, staffing. Communication and motivations and with decision making process for accomplishment of goals and objectives.

MANAGEMENT IS SCIENCE:

Management is a systematic body of knowledge and apply it for the overall growth and development of organisation. therefore, the management is a social science since, it deals with social behaviour of human beings. It is not possible to study the human behaviour in science labs. It studies the psychology and reactions, feelings of human beings under working conditions and working performance in a working environment among group. For this Mc. Gregor theory 'X and Y' has been formulated. Management scientist is organisational leader who leads the organisation keeping view of its objectives and goals.

MANAGEMENT IS AN ART:

Management is an art when a management professional applies his experience, talent, and knowledge in processing the implementation of decision making. Henry Fayal's Principles of management and management concepts must be applied in the management activities and functions. Talent will improve through the experience. Experience will come through regular practice. Learning the works, continuously doing the works., training to the workers will expertise in works. Management must provide training, directing, and monitoring the works of staff leads to experience.

MANAGEMENT AS PROFESSION:

In the opinion of Peter Drucker, a famous writer on management felt that the government should not control the management. He strongly believed that the managers are well versed with only by their performance and results and accomplishment of organisational goals and objectives and not as per their academic qualifications, merit ranks obtained in their degrees. Professionalism in management through the efficiency in works good will of the organisations. It has been proved in case of many organisations like State Bank of India, Tata Consultancy Services (TCS), BHEL., ECIL., NTPC., ONGC., and Indian oil Corporation. Behind the success of these organisations, the great efforts of management unforgettable. Its Benchmark and yardstick to the performance of the management. They proved the management is the heart of the above organisations. Management is not hereditary, it is by talent, dedicated commitment, applying knowledge and experience in decision implementation. Management should always be target oriented., customer centric.

MANAGEMENT VS. ADMINISTRATION:

Peter F Drucker suggested that the management is applicable in business, while administration is applicable in government offices and, also in company administrations on routine day to day functioning through H.R. The following are some areas, in which clear cut differences shall be observed.

Table. No. 1. Administration vs. Management

Point	Administration	Management
1. Name	Strategically thinking function	Executory function by H.R. staff

2. Scope	Major issues and Policies	Implementation of plans
3. Status Level	Higher level function	Middle and lower-level function
4. Skills., Excellence	Conceptual and human	Technological and manual skills
5. Represents	in government functioning	H. R. staff
6. Usefulness	Mostly in government	Mostly in Business

Fig. No. 1. The Three Dimensions of Management

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE MANAGEMENT STUDY:

Management just like central nervous system and functioning with brain in the organisational body. If the central system and brain in the human body has been affected, treated him as brain dead case. The same, as in the case of management in the organisational body also, if it was defunct or inefficient, it impacts, on its productivity, sales, profitability, financial performance, credit wordiness and even on its survival in competitive world.

Therefore, the role of management is crucial in the organisation. Timely and appropriate decision making, delegation of powers, decentralisation, unity of direction and unity of command of management leads to success in the organisation. For the effective functioning of management, experienced and most efficient people must be recruited as management personnel for the implementation of decisions taken by the board of directors keeping view of the overall growth of development of the organisation. Policy decisions should be taken keeping in view of the ground realities, financial soundness, H.R. capabilities, resources allotment, infrastructure availability. Working conditions and motivational and inspiring incentives to staff.

Management should keep ready all the infrastructure, resources., H.R. cooperation and coordination while taking the decisions on the targets of production, sales, profitability, marketability etc., Management teaches lessons practically on all these aspects, how the strategic decisions should be taken, what are the factors to determine to take such decisions, how to face challenges in the market with our counter strategies. These are all depends upon the efficient managerial decision- making powers with all pre-planned readiness.

ORGANSATION VS. MANAGEMENT:

Organisation is one of the important executive functions. Management will concentrate to implement the predetermined plans of the management into execution through the

organisational objectives for the accomplishment goals and targets. As opined by Robbins and Mary Coulter, ‘Organisation meant for in determining what tasks are to be done, who is to execute them, how those tasks are to be bifurcated, reporting authority, and where the decisions are to be taken’. Therefore, the organisation is the identifying and grouping of work to be executed defining the delegating of authority and establishing the relationships to enable people to work together to accomplish objectives and goals. Thus, according to I.A Allen, Process of identifying and grouping the work to be performed, defining and delegation of authority and responsibility and establishing the relationships for the purpose of enabling people to work most efficiently together in accomplishing the goals and objectives. The organisation dedicates to achieve common goals. Division of works between the workers facilitates to entrusts the works among the suitable, identified, and trained workers. Koontz Donnel, correctly said that each organisation is structural relationship by which an enterprise is bound together and the framework in which individual effort is well coordinated.

Whereas the management is decision making body, goal oriented, it works, plans, executes behind the screen, it is intangible. Management is a trouble shooter, goal oriented and growth oriented, Management is a dynamic-body, and it is a multi-disciplinary organ. Management made easy the works through the delegation of powers and delegation authority. Behind every successful organisation, management efficiency, management supportive efforts will be there. Without management, the business unit or organisation is only mere aimless group.

Fig. No. 2. Organisation vs. Management Balance

HENRY FAYOL’S PRINCIPLES OF MANAGEMENT:

Henry Fayol was a French mining Engineer turned as a leading industrialist and successful Manager. He has been considered as “Father of Administrative Management theory with focus on the development of broad administrative principles applicable to general and higher managerial levels. He wrote a book in French in 1916 and published in English in 1949 with the title “General and Industrial Management” which is now to be one of classical study of

management. Henry Fayol designed the principles management with 14 major principles to be followed by every management in the organisation for the accomplishment of objectives and goals., as follows. With his own practical experience in his mining corporation. With these principles he made easy and facilitated the managements in the reaching the goals and accomplishing the objectives in the organisations

Table. No. 2. Henri Fayol's 14 Principles of Management

No.	Principle	No.	Principle
1.	Division of Labour	2.	Authority and Responsibility
3.	Discipline	4.	Unity of Command
5.	Unity of Direction	6.	Subordination of Individual interest to group Interest
7.	Remuneration to personnel	8.	Centralisation
9.	Scalar chain	10.	Order
11.	Equity	12.	Stability of tenure of personnel
13.	Initiative	14.	Esprit De Corp

Fig. No. 3. Henry Fayol's 14 Principles of Management

EVALUATION OF PRINCIPLES OF MANAGEMENT

Henry Fayol Principles of management are not hard and rigid rules of management. They are very easy to understand and to follow. They are for smooth running of the management functioning in the organisation. While executing the managerial functions., the principles of management are the helping tools. “ It is the matter of knowledge how to make use of them which is difficult art of requiring intelligence, experience, decision and proportion” since the management is common for all organisations, Fayol argued that those who acquire general knowledge of managerial functions and principles can manage all types of organisations. He further noticed that anyone interested in managing a corporate business organisation or a small enterprise must learn these principles and apply successfully.

FUNCTIONS OF MANAGEMENT:

In the organisation, the role of management is very important and dynamic. Main activity of management is to get the things done through men appointed for that through motivating and providing training and with directing them controlling activities in the organisations. Management in every organisation must perform five major functions like planning, directing, controlling, coordinating, and staffing. Every manager must possess leadership qualities in getting the things done from the workers through tactful motivating skills and administrative capabilities creating

Better working conditions. For extracting the work from the workers, encouraging wage policy, facilities, medical facilities, motivational incentives, promotional policy should also be there to efficient workers. They must encourage the workers in all aspect avoiding labour unrest.

According to Henry Fayol, the manager in the organisation is to perform certain special operating and executive functions like Human Resources, finance, production, material management and information technology. The following are the main functions of the management in the organisation. They are the Planning, Direction Organising, Staffing, and controlling.

Planning: Planning is defined, by which manager decides the mission and objectives of the organisation and try to accomplish them. Prediction of future growth and development of the organisation estimates and assess the market demand, supply, and promotion of sales., by the managers.

Organisation: Goals, objectives, and targets are accomplished through the group of workers according to the predetermined objectives and goals. For the accomplishment of these, right works are assigned to right persons on division of labour technique. By thorough monitoring and supervising., quality in works will be maintained.

Direction: It is concerned with leading and direction towards achievement of organisational goals. With proper motivation, training to the workers., predetermined targets and objectives and goals will be achieved.

Staffing: For the achievement of objectives and to get the works done, the H.R. recruitment and selection of skilled, semi-skilled and unskilled staff administrative, technology, hardware and software staff members are very much required. Selected staff will be trained, assigned the works to right persons at right places.

Controlling: Management main function is to control the staff imposing working conditions with rules and regulations to maintain the workers at the work- place fixing the targets and assess the evaluation of the performance appraisal. Setting standards performance, measuring performance, comparison of actual work performance is the function of controlling.

Fig. No. 4. Five Functions of Management

MANAGEMENT BY OBJECTIVES (M.B.O):

Since long time, process of setting the objectives and targets was the duty of top-level management. The secondary short-term objectives and goals were fixed by the middle-level management keeping in view of common objectives of organisation. The lower level of management concentrates only on execution of assigned objectives and goals for its accomplishment. Later, with the changing attitude of workforce and their working culture attitude led to find out new method of management. These new developments gave birth to the evolution of “Management by Objectives” (M.B.O). Management by Objectives, and self-control as the basis of measuring the performance of managers.

In, 1961 Edward Shelh, advocated management by objectives as means of integrating individuals with the organisation. In 1965 John Humble, a British Management Consultant, published a book “Management by Objectives” which is later known as in other concept as “Management by Result. And as. ”Goals Management”. In recent times, ‘Management by Objectives’ has become a philosophy of managing in many enterprises. It is being recognised as the most dynamic and exciting area of strategic formulative management.

Management is for the accomplishment of objectives, predetermined goal set in the organisation through its executive functions like planning, direction, controlling, staffing, and coordinating. Management will have to perform other operative and executive functions like Production Management, Financial Management, H.R. Management, sales Management and Accounts management. In every stream of management separate objectives and goals are to be fixed and to accomplish. The concerned management will take care of accomplishment of objectives and goals of the stream of management.

Management by objectives (M.B.O) set the goals and targets and fix the responsibility to staff and departments for their achievement and help to set their future course of action planning to the organisations. It also guides the employees to understand their assignments at their work- place.

Table. No. 3. FEATURES OF MANAGEMENT BY OBJECTIVES:

Point	Feature Description
A	Joint Goal Setting: Superiors, subordinates, officers, and executives will jointly accomplish the objectives.
B	Joint Decision: Objectives of the organisation are jointly examined and decided by superiors and subordinates.
C	Joint Action Plan: Superiors and subordinates jointly decide how to accomplish and attain the objectives.
D	Motivation: Through M.B.O. objectives can be accomplished maximum by motivating subordinates.
E	Superior Support: Support from the superior is always available to the subordinates in the process of attaining objectives.
F	Clarity: In definition, the objectives can be clearly defined and clarified clearly for their success.
G	Social Conformance: The objectives fixed by the organisation should be helpful to society (conformance to public need).
H	Multiplicity: The organisation has several objectives related to marketing, sales, profitability, productivity, growth, and development of the organisation, according to P.F. Drucker.
I	Attainability: The framed objectives should be achievable, practically.
J	Evaluation Mechanism: M.B.O sets an evaluation mechanism individual-wise, department-wise, and function-wise to check whether objectives are accomplished or not.

MANAGEMENT DECISION MAKING:

Decision making is an important activity of the management. It is a challenging activity of management particularly in finance, investment and. also in purchase of assets incurring huge expenditure and in launching new innovative product. Crucial decision making is a vital element of good management because the decisions are helpful for solving the problems. Decision making is not so easy task. It needs historical data, analysis, discussions, approvals, logical reasoning, and critical evaluation of various alternatives. It is a lengthy procedure. The success of management depends upon the quality decision making and seriousness in its implementation. Different authors are expressed their opinions on decision making concept.

“Decision making is the selection based on some criteria from two or more possible alternatives.

...George or Terry

“Decision making is a process through which managers identify organisational problems and attempt to resolve it”
 ..Bartol and Martin.

Table. No. 4. FEATURES OF DECISION MAKING:

Point	Feature	Description
A	Goal-Oriented	Decisions are made to achieve specific goals and targets.
B	Dual Activity	Characterized by the dual activities of search for and selection from alternatives.
C	Intellectual Process	An application of critical thinking, logical reasoning, and intellectual ability.
D	Dynamic Process	A dynamic process involving management's discretion and judgment.
E	Continuous Activity	It is an ongoing, continuous activity, not a one-time event.
F	Core of Planning	Koontz & O'Donnell observed that decision making is the core of planning and is situational in nature.
G	Social Activity	It is a social activity that involves human analytical thinking and logical conclusion.

Table. No. 5. PROCESS OF DECISION MAKING

Step No.	Activity
1	Setting Objectives
2	Identifying the Problem
3	Diagnosing the problem
4	Establishing Objectives
5	Collection of related information
6	Developing Alternatives
7	Evaluating alternatives
8	Making a final selection of choice
9	Implementing the choice
10	Feedback on its implementation

FIVE SUPER-NATURAL POWERS OF MANAGEMENT:

Management of an organisation extracts the work from the concerned staff, workers, H.R. Executive in a predetermined targeted manner with all resources and inputs for the accomplishment of objectives, pre-planned goals. In the process of accomplishment of objectives, management acts as Central nervous system and heart of the organisation body. Organisation in this process will execute and implement decisions taken by the management for achieving the goals.

Management will accomplish the predetermined goals through getting the done with support of “FIVE SUPER-NATURAL POWERS” 1. Human Resources., 2. Raw material., 3. Machine Power., 4. Procedural methodology and 5. Financial investment Power under the leadership of management in the organisation.

Fig. No. 5. Foundations of Management Success

MODERN APPROACHES OF MANAGEMENT IN THE ORGANISATION: SCIENTIFIC MANAGEMENT

Consequent of II world war, the then governments of various countries started the promoting productivity with modern methods to improve the workers efficiency and productivity using scientific technology. It is called Scientific and modern approach in the process of productivity. “Scientific management is an approach that emphasizes the scientific study of work “. Scientific management aims at producing more export-quality product in bulk quantity and at an affordable cost of production. Scientific Management aims at optimum utilisation of all super-natural resources like human resources, raw material resources, machine power., procedural methodology and financial investment power to improve overall efficiency of the quality productivity of organisation minimising the cost of production also by minimising the wastage in the usage of cost elements.

The Father of scientific management Frederic W. Taylor is the founder of scientific management. He considers time study, standards, scientific approach in predetermined goals., monetary incentives to work force as an inspiration. He wrote a book on the principles of scientific management in 1911.

F.W Taylor basically a mechanical engineer having interest in the research on scientific management. He developed the practical working theory on the functioning of scientific management. His observations are as follow for slow work., and inefficiency in productivity and suggested remedies also.

- F.W. Tayler felt that wage system was one of the major reasons for slow work. He introduced piece rate incentive system which will reward and award the efficient workers who produced well with quality. It has been inspired the workers.
- He also introduced time and motion study. It has been inspired the workers greatly.
- Unnecessary moments are removed to find out the best way of doing a job. Jobs are sub-divided into small units.
- He tried to achieve efficiency with time rate system.
- He established cordial relations between workers and management so that

management can extract the work from the workers in the desired way.

His theory of scientific management is that the employees are motivated. Productivity can be increased when the right person engaged for a right job. Workers' interest and capability is very important than the project task. Workers are to be paid but not the job, Increased wage incentives for increased productivity helps in increasing productivity. F.W. theory has been mostly implemented in the Ford Motor Company, resulting of his implementation in the Ford company, with reduced cost of production which causes lowering price determination. Increased the market share of Ford cars.

DELEGATION OF POWERS AND DECENTRALISATION:

The success of management in an organisation will be under the process of Decentralisation and delegation of powers only. Powers should not be centralised only under the top Management. It very difficult to run the organisation if the powers centralised. According to the experience, capability, efficiency certain powers should be delegated to subordinate officers at the Manager level of a department. Then the decisions will be taken very quickly. Delegation of authority is very important and inevitable in the organisation. Centralisation of powers in the hands of top-level managements leads slow in decision making and unnecessary delay in works, inefficiency, low productivity etc. Supervisory powers, purchasing powers, financial delegation of powers up to certain level and decision-making powers should be transferred to lower level efficient, and most experienced well qualified, Chief Accountant and Chief Cashier level who are the most responsible and trusted officials at manager and supervisory levels. Then the work will not be held up. Therefore, the delegation of authority is nothing but assigning certain work to other capable, efficient and to an experienced person.

In the opinion of F.C. Moore, "Delegation means assigning work to the others and giving them authority to do so"

As opined by Koontz and O' Donnell. "The entire process of delegation involves the determination of results expected, the assignment of task, the delegation of authority for accomplishment of these tasks, and the extraction of responsibility for their accomplishment"

CHARACTERISTICS OF DELEGATION OF POWERS & DECENTRALISATION:

1. No Complete delegation of powers and Authority. In the management full power of delegation cannot be made to the subordinate managers of departments concerned. Simple powers up to certain limits powers will be delegated lower-level managers and supervisors.
2. Managers will not delegate the authority to a subordinate which himself not exercising. It means that no manager will transfer the powers which he is not in possession.
3. Delegation of powers and authority keeping view of organisational interest in the accomplishment of objectives.
4. Delegations of authority and powers will made to subordinates only higher authorities feel it necessary for smooth running of organisation, that to minor powers administrative powers., and limited financial powers.
5. Higher level management will delegate the authority and powers to the subordinate management staff, supervisory staff as a part job responsibility or assignment of work

as per the eligibility and capability. While delegating the powers to subordinates everybody must feel with these elements.

ADOPTION OF TECHNOLOGY, IT & ICT, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE H.R. MANAGEMENT PORTFOLIO

It is the technology and digital era. Entire world is electronic hub running with technology. Manufacturing, marketing, transportation, supply chain management, finance & banking organisations, administration & accounts departments, taxation and audit, science & Defence, space technology, educational and Insurance sector, in stock exchange, trading activities, service sector organisations, Medical, Health & hospital management, tourism department, endowment spiritual and temple organisations etc., everywhere almost in every field and sector adopted and implemented

I.T and ICT in their portfolio.

Moreover, the artificial intelligence is the emerging technology now available in the hands of management for the analysis of the data and to take appropriate timely decision for the growth and development the organisations.

In the recruitment & selections process of H.R. staff. and in the allotment of work assignments, pay roll calculation, H.R. accounting process and in the evaluation of workers and staff performance appraisal, grading, ranking the employees now at present the Artificial intelligence is being widely used.

Specially in the financial, accounting, tax assessments, tax calculations, preparation of organisational accounting statements annual periodical returns, production sales and target statements for the higher authorities, technology, artificial intelligence, computerised systems and automation process is being widely used in the organisations.

Fig. No. 6. Role of Artificial Intelligence Across Key Business Domains

ELEMENTS OF DELEGATION OF POWERS:

- A. RESPONSIBILITY:** Assignment of work to a lower-level subordinate with certain powers, is not actually feeling of Authority but a feeling of responsibility to the subordinates. The must complete the additional task given with responsibility with much dedication and commitment with teamwork.
- B. AUTHORITY:** To make it complete the assigned work successfully certain powers are also to be exercised as delegated by the higher-level management. Tactfully the

powers are to be exercised only to complete the work and for harming the colleagues. To take the important decisions, those powers are to be exercised to complete work successfully.

- C. ANSWERBILITY AND ACCOUNTABILITY:** Th additional responsibility assigned to suitable and capable subordinate management with the delegated powers must be answerable to the higher-level management. Results, targeted objectives if fixed to him must be accomplished using the delegated powers with the coordination and cooperation of staff.

CONCLUSION:

This chapter is designed as overall conceptual round up of the management in an organisation. The dynamics which are very much essential for the modern management for smooth running of an organisation in accomplishment of objectives and target were elaborated for the better understanding of targeted stakeholders i.e., M.B.A students, management professionals and management trainees. Modern approaches of management, Scientific management, Management by Objectives., Decision making powers, delegation and, decentralisation process, are excellently helpful for the overall growth and development of organisation through the functions and principles of management. Different level of managements i.e., Top-level management and middle-level management and lower-level subordinate management will coordinate each other work together in accomplishing predetermined targets, objectives and, goals.

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